

README:

The virtual machine image (Vneo4j.ova) contains all the necessary environments and tools to run our experiment. The username and password of the virtual machine are as follows:

Username: vneo4j

Password: vneo4j

The following list introduces the content in each folder:

- ~/Data/Databases: examples of the Neo4j databases, each with their own separate folders. Two databases are loaded and ready to run: graphProductLine and toybox
- ~/Data/neo4j-browser: the source code for *Neo4j* Browser. All the required tools to run *Neo4j* Browser are installed and ready to start.
- ~/Data/query: examples of analysis that could be executed with *Neo4j* Browser

The following instruction will walk you through the process of running *Neo4j* Browser. In this example, we will use graphProductLine database and the analysis executed in query...

- Go to folder ~/Data/Databases/graphProductLine, use the following command to start the database:
 - o bin/neo4j start
- You should see the following output:

```
vneo4j@ubuntu:~/Data/Databases/graphProductLine$ bin/neo4j start
Directories in use:
home:           /home/vneo4j/Data/Databases/graphProductLine
config:         /home/vneo4j/Data/Databases/graphProductLine/conf
logs:           /home/vneo4j/Data/Databases/graphProductLine/logs
plugins:        /home/vneo4j/Data/Databases/graphProductLine/plugins
import:         /home/vneo4j/Data/Databases/graphProductLine/import
data:           /home/vneo4j/Data/Databases/graphProductLine/data
certificates:   /home/vneo4j/Data/Databases/graphProductLine/certificates
licenses:       /home/vneo4j/Data/Databases/graphProductLine/licenses
run:            /home/vneo4j/Data/Databases/graphProductLine/run
Starting Neo4j.
WARNING: Max 4096 open files allowed, minimum of 40000 recommended. See the Neo4j manual.
Started neo4j (pid:2949). It is available at http://localhost:7472
There may be a short delay until the server is ready.
```

- Next got to folder ~/Data/neo4j-browser, use the following command to start the *Neo4j* Browser.
 - o yarn start
- You should see the following output:

```
Child worker:
          Asset      Size  Chunks      Chunk Names
bolt-worker-252bd47d8baa9f78b345.js 8.14 MiB   main [emitted] [immutable] main
Entrypoint main = bolt-worker-252bd47d8baa9f78b345.js
[./node_modules/core-js/internals/path.js] 71 bytes {main} [built]
[./node_modules/core-js/modules/es.aggregate-error.js] 1.45 KiB {main} [built]
[./node_modules/core-js/modules/es.array-buffer.constructor.js] 556 bytes {main} [built]
[./node_modules/core-js/modules/es.array-buffer.is-view.js] 397 bytes {main} [built]
[./node_modules/core-js/modules/es.array-buffer.slice.js] 1.46 KiB {main} [built]
[./node_modules/core-js/modules/es.array.concat.js] 2.37 KiB {main} [built]
[./node_modules/core-js/modules/es.array.copy-within.js] 428 bytes {main} [built]
[./node_modules/core-js/stable/index.js] 9.46 KiB {main} [built]
[./node_modules/ts-loader/index.js?!../src/shared/services/bolt/boltWorker.ts] ./node_modules/ts-loader??ref--17-1!./src/shared/services/bolt/boltWorker.ts 4.46 KiB {main} [built]
[./src/shared/services/bolt/boltConnection.ts] 6.1 KiB {main} [built]
[./src/shared/services/bolt/boltConnectionErrors.ts] 662 bytes {main} [built]
[./src/shared/services/bolt/boltMappings.ts] 19.1 KiB {main} [built]
[./src/shared/services/bolt/boltWorkerMessages.ts] 2.94 KiB {main} [built]
[./src/shared/services/bolt/transactions.ts] 5.29 KiB {main} [built]
[./src/shared/services/exceptions.ts] 4.27 KiB {main} [built]
+ 1358 hidden modules
i [wdm]: Compiled successfully.
No issues found.
```

- Wait for a few seconds and open Firefox Web Browser. It should access localhost:8080 and automatically open the browser. You should see the following output:

- If you are prompted to input login credentials, use:
 - o Connect URL: localhost:7682
 - o Database Username: neo4j
 - o Password: vneo4j
- As an example, you can run the call graph query stored in ~/Data/query/. Paste the content of the file on the top bar and click the play button on the left.

```
1 MATCH (p:cFunction)
2 CALL apoc.path.expandConfig(p, {
3   relationshipFilter: 'call',
4   labelFilter: 'cFunction',
5   minLevel: 1
6 })
7 YIELD path WITH path, head(nodes(path)) AS a, head(relationships(path)) AS r, last(nodes(path)) AS b
8 WHERE (NOT a.label CONTAINS 'k') OR (NOT b.label CONTAINS 'k')
9 RETURN a, r, b
10 LIMIT 45
```

- You should see the following output:

- Feel free to explore the visualization. You can use the bottom left buttons to zoom in/out, maximize the frame by clicking on the fullscreen icon on the top left corner, create filters with the small form on the left sidebar or opening the tabular view.

If you want to change the database being queried:

- Stop the current active database:
 - o Got to `~Data/Databases/graphProductLine`
 - o Run `bin/neo4j stop`
- Move to a `~Data/Databases/toybox`
- Reload *Neo4j* Browser on the Firefox and feel free to query the database